

Factors Influencing Students' Enrollment Decisions in Higher Education Institutions: A Case Study of the National University of Battambang

Chang Chhor ,
Sokha Hoern
Graduate School, National University of Battambang, Cambodia

Abstract

This study examines the factors influencing students' enrollment decisions at the National University of Battambang (NUBB), Cambodia. Specifically, it aims to (1) identify the key factors shaping students' enrollment decisions, (2) analyze students' perceptions of these factors, and (3) explore gender-based differences in enrollment decisions. A quantitative research approach was adopted, surveying 350 first-year students using a structured questionnaire comprising 33 items across seven categories. The analysis highlights four significant factors influencing enrollment decisions: parental influence, prospective career opportunities, family support, and personal characteristics. Conversely, the university's reputation and multidisciplinary aspects did not show statistically significant effects. Gender analysis revealed a significant difference in family influence, with females reporting more potent effects than males. These findings underscore the need for higher education institutions to prioritize personalized support systems, career development initiatives, and strategies to address gender-specific needs to enhance student enrollment. Recommendations include strengthening family engagement strategies and refining university offerings to align with students' career aspirations and personal goals.

Keywords: *higher education institutions, student's professional development, student's enrollment decision.*

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Introduction

The term education originated from the Latin phrase Educare, which translates to "to teach, train, or extract knowledge." Education has a significant effect on everyone's lives. Education is considered a vital human right. Independence and empowerment benefit all those involved (Sharma & Ankit, 2023). While skill development and education are vital for economic success, do they outweigh other factors influencing GDP growth? According to projections from the Bureau of Labor Statistics

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Multifactor Productivity Program, educational attainment may not be as significant for economic development as previously thought (Hulten, 2017; Chork et al., 2024). Higher education is also a crucial driver of economic development. Many countries, such as Cambodia, have invested heavily in improving their higher education sector because of its importance. Cambodia has experienced significant expansion in higher education institutions (HEIs) over the past two decades (since 1997). Despite tremendous institutional expansion, quality challenges in Cambodian higher education persist (Ban & Heng, 2023; Huot et al., 2024; Tieng, 2023). Countries expect higher education to fulfill three important roles in and for society: 1. To support innovation through knowledge generation, global access, and local adaptation; 2. Contributing to human capital building by training a trained and flexible labor force, including high-level scientists, professionals, technicians, elementary and secondary school teachers, and future governments, civil services, and corporate leaders; 3. Laying the groundwork for democracy, nation-building, and social cohesiveness (World Bank, 2002; Thay, 2024).

Following the violent Khmer Rouge era (1975--1979), Cambodia's education system was forced to start over. Through numerous legislative reforms and efforts, the Cambodian government, its development partners, and other concerned nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) have collaborated to improve the quality and equity of the education system (Heng, et al, 2022; Sam et al., 2012a; Sam et al., 2012b; Sam et al., 2013). Higher education is critical for leading students toward their intended occupations and preparing them for the job. In Cambodia, however, the low quality and ineffectiveness of higher education institutions (HEIs) have hampered graduates' potential, resulting in challenges such as skill mismatches, work-life conflicts, and job unhappiness (Ek & Muth, 2023). Cambodia has 130 higher education institutions, including 48 public and 82 private institutions located in 20 provinces and the capital, Phnom Penh. Higher education institutions are overseen by 16 different ministries and institutions. From 2019--2020, 170,246 students sought a bachelor's degree, with 86,158 females accounting for 50.60% of the sample. However, there was a decline of 937 students (0.55 percent) in female enrollment (MOEYS, 2022). Rapid growth and growing demand also intensify rivalry among HEIs to attract students throughout the country. Thus, HEIs are increasing their marketing efforts by improving their marketing mix attributes. This includes updating its recruitment/staffing procedures, which are crucial in today's competitive landscape, as well as identifying the factors that are critical to student requirements and goals (Mehboob et al, 2012).

The objectives of research are as follows:

1. To investigate the factors influencing students' enrollment decisions at NUBB
2. To understand students' perceptions of the factors influencing their enrollment decisions at NUBB
3. To determine whether there is a significant difference in students' enrollment decisions between male and female students at NUBB.

The Theoretical Basis

Numerous studies have examined the elements that influence students' decisions to attend universities or colleges. Several variables have been identified and studied to assess their impact on students' university or college choices (Mehboob et al, 2012).

University Reputation

Institutional image and reputation have a significant effect on college selection. College reputation has a significant effect on prospective students during their college search and selection process (Ming, 2010). A reputable institution is one that has a positive reputation in the community, is trusted by parents and guardians, has well-respected leadership, and students value their degree on the basis of the university's image. Some academics have examined the performance of various universities and created evaluation models on the basis of the aspects that influence reputation (Khoi, 2020; Spearman et al., 2016). According to Fernandez (2010), when choosing a postsecondary institution, students should evaluate not only the programs provided but also the integrity and reputation of the brand. Student happiness is an important research topic in today's competitive academic environment. Graduates who are satisfied with their education can be a great endorsement for universities. Satisfied students can benefit the university in various ways, including by recommending it to others, spreading positive word-of-mouth, and remaining loyal (Qazi et al, 2021).

Multidisciplinary Aspects

The term 'multidisciplinary' consists of two words. The first word is 'multi', which indicates the number of words or more than one. The second word is 'disciplinary', which refers to a specific field of study. The term 'multidisciplinary' refers to the use of multiple disciplines as autonomous learning components. This allows students to work within specified constraints and achieve discipline-specific goals (Sharma, 2023). On the basis of Monsen et al (2012), a multidisciplinary approach aims to optimize rehabilitation at all ICF levels, including body functioning, activity, and involvement. Multidisciplinary levels are categorized on the basis of collaboration levels, as shown below:

- (A) Interdisciplinary teams collaborate to achieve common aims.
- (B) Multidisciplinary professionals collaborate with the same person, but each works within their own professional boundaries and may not be aware of each other's practices.
- (C) Transdisciplinary: experts integrate their expertise with that of other team members.
- (D) Undiscipline/intradisciplinary - focuses solely on one's vocation.

HEI staff and students view lifelong learning as a continuous learning opportunity that extends beyond formal education. Lifelong learning is viewed as a personal activity that requires institutional support to accelerate learning and provide necessary content for meaningful lives, job advancement, and sustainability. In effect, lifelong learning is undertaken in a multidisciplinary manner but discreetly. It is not adequately integrated and articulated into higher education curricula and pedagogical practices to promote lifelong learning. Lifelong learning requires individual endeavors, institutional efforts, and possibilities for HEI personnel and students, as well as the community (Biney et al, 2023).

Peer Influence

Young individuals may emulate their classmates' decisions about their future education, especially if they are unsure about their own goals. Peers are also likely to provide feedback on teenagers' expectations when future-related concerns are discussed in the peer group (Kiruru, 2008). Pistolessi (2022) also showed that an

individual's choices upon entering higher education are also subject to the academic achievement level of their peers. Additionally, a study by James and Denis (2015) discovered that peer relationships affect students' program choices.

Prospective Career Opportunities

Making career decisions is a complex process that requires students to have a deep understanding of themselves (Azhenov et al., 2023). Career growth is an ongoing process for many individuals. They explore various job opportunities available in the market and choose among them. Azizzadeh et al. (2003), on the basis of a study of medical science students, reported that career opportunities combined with prestige are the most important factors in the decision-making process for selecting a surgical career. While it is often believed that family and community influence workplace willingness, this decision significantly impacts students' career paths, opening and closing various opportunities for them. The job opportunities within a program significantly impact the choices that students make (Geiger & Ogilby, 2000). According to Pascual (2014), students' primary consideration when choosing a university course is the availability of job opportunities, which significantly influences their choice of major program.

Family Influences

Parenting style refers to the emotional environment in which children are raised. There are four main parenting styles outlined in the literature: permissive, authoritative, neglectful, and authoritarian. The authoritarian parenting style is characterized by high levels of control and demands, along with low warmth and responsiveness (Moon-Seo et al, 2021). According to Puccioni (2018), parental involvement in children's schoolwork at home, including homework, plays a crucial role in predicting school readiness. As a result, children who are well prepared for school are more likely to experience positive academic outcomes, such as the development of positive social behaviors and the achievement of academic success.

According to Kyui (2010), educational reforms in Russia from 1995--2006 significantly increased the influence of family income on college enrollment, particularly for full-tuition programs. Additionally, family income plays a greater role than parents' educational background in determining which colleges students attend on the basis of the quality of education offered.

Students' college selection depends on various factors, such as academic quality, facilities, the campus environment, and personal traits (Mehboob et al, 2012). According to Jain (2014), income plays a significant role in students' choice between public and private education. The location of a college also strongly influences students' selection of higher education institutions (HEIs), and visiting a university campus has been identified as a crucial factor to consider. These factors are essential when making decisions about higher education.

Personal Characteristics (PCs)

Higher education (HE) has always played a crucial role in a country's development. In Angola, following the civil war in 2002, there was a significant expansion in higher education opportunities. Since then, there has been a strong commitment to increasing access to higher education for young people. This led to the development of a comprehensive policy aimed at establishing new higher education institutions (HEIs), both public and private, setting high standards for HE regulation and implementing internal and external scholarship programs to actively promote the pursuit of higher

education (Gaspar & Soares, 2021; Lan et al., 2024a). Colleges have minimal influence on individual student characteristics, but there is a clear correlation between student traits and college selection. For example, socioeconomic status significantly influences the type of college a student is likely to attend. Students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds are more inclined to enroll in four-year universities, whereas those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds tend to opt for two-year institutions (Chapman, 1981; Lan et al., 2024b).

Students' Enrollment Decisions

According to Baharun et al. (2011), quality education, decision influence, customer focus, cost, facility, socialization, and location are strong factors that influence a student's decision in higher education. According to Dhaliwal et al. (2019), several important factors influence the process of admission to private universities in the country. Most students consider the admission fee, additional expenses, and quality of education offered by the university when choosing their preferred private university. The social identity of the university and its societal significance also play a role in influencing students' decisions. The selection of a university for graduation can be explained through three models on the basis of student behavior and the factors mentioned above. These models are financial/econometric models, status fulfillment/sociological models, and combined models. The prime factors that influence students' college choice decisions include educational costs and financial obligations (Callender & Melis, 2022). Recently, finding a job has become a major concern for students and their families. The decision to enroll in a specific educational institution is influenced by various factors related to employment, and employment opportunities are a significant predictor of enrollment decisions (Jain, 2014).

Figure1. Conceptual Framework

Methods

Participants

The study's sample comprised first-year students who were purposively selected from a pool of 350 students at the National University of Battambang. These students were both male and female and aged between 18 and 25 years. Their native language is Khmer, and they are proficient in English as a second language. The survey questionnaires they completed involved the selection of multiple-choice answers. This

approach aimed to enhance the reliability of the research and shed light on the factors influencing first-year students' decisions to enroll in higher education institutions. The specific focus of the research was on the National University of Battambang (NUBB).

Research Tools and Instruments

A survey questionnaire was developed with the study's objectives in mind. The questionnaire was distributed to the students for completion. It consists of multiple-choice questions familiar to the students. The researchers used a paper-based method to collect the data, aiming to create a closer connection between the researcher and the participants. The participants were required to select one of four response options for each question (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= agree, and 4= strongly agree). The survey questionnaire is divided into two sections: section 1 gathers participants' personal information through three questions.

Research Location

The current research is being conducted at the National University of Battambang, which is located on National Road Number 5 in Prek Preah Sdach District, Battambang city, Battambang Province, Cambodia.

Research Design

This study utilizes a quantitative research design and conducts a survey at the National University of Battambang. The participants consisted of 350 first-year students enrolled at the university. Paper survey questionnaires were employed as tools for data collection. The collected data were analyzed to identify the factors influencing students' enrollment decisions in higher education institutions, with a specific focus on the case of the National University of Battambang.

Table 1. Questionnaire Reliability

Variables	Number of items	Alpha
University Reputation (UR)	4	.804
Multi-Disciplinary Aspects (MD)	4	.730
Peer Influence (PI)	5	.761
Prospective Career Opportunity (CO)	5	.824
Family Influences (FI)	5	.721
Personal Characteristic (PC)	5	.870
Students' enrollment Decision (SE)	5	.689

A Likert scale was also used to obtain targeted responses from participants on each item of the questionnaire. The 4-point Likert scale is interpreted as follows:

Table 2. Factors Influencing Students' Enrollment Decisions in Higher Education Institutions

Scale	Continuum	Description
4	3.26-4.00	Strongly agree
3	2.51-3.25	Agree
2	1.76-2.50	Disagree
1	1.00-1.76	Strongly Disagree

Results

The following results are explained via mean rank interpretation:

Table 3. Demographic Profile of the Participants

Demographic/Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	181	51.7%
	Female	169	48.3%
Age	18-22	307	87.8%
	23-25	35	10%
	25-above	8	2.3%
Major	Social Science	183	52.3%
	Applied Science	167	47.7%

The table reveals a notable gender imbalance among the 350 participants, with 51.7% (181) male and 48.3% (169) female students, highlighting a greater percentage of male students in the study. The majority of respondents are in the **18–22 years of age range**, representing a substantial **87.8%** of the sample. A smaller portion of the sample falls within the **23–25 age range (10%)**, and even fewer are **25 years and above (2.3%)**.

Findings based on Research Question one: What are the key factors that influence students' enrollment decisions at NUBB?

Table 4 Regression Coefficients and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Relationship	Beta	SE	T value	Sig.	Decision
H1	UR→SE	.054	.070	0.944	.346	Rejected
H2	MD→SE	.050	.080	0.831	.406	Rejected
H3	PI→SE	.171	.037	3.950	.000	Supported
H4	CO→SE	.138	.065	2.094	.037	Supported
H5	FI→SE	.203	.044	4.287	.000	Supported
H6	PC→SE	.302	.064	4.841	.000	Supported

The analyses show that PI (H3) has a significant positive effect on SE ($\beta=0.171$, $p=0.000$). This means that as PI increases, SE also increases. CO has a significant positive effect on SE ($\beta=0.138$, $p=0.037$), which means that as AUT increases, so does SE. FI (H5) has a strong, highly significant positive effect ($\beta=0.203$, $p=0.000$). PC (H6) has a significant positive effect on SE ($\beta=0.302$, $p=0.000$). This means that as PC increases, SE also increases. Therefore, the relationships between H3, H4, H5, H6 and SE are well supported. On the other hand, UR(H1) has no significant effect on SE ($\beta=0.054$, $p=0.346$). This means that the UR does not affect SE. However, MD (H2) had no significant effect on SE ($\beta=0.050$, $p=0.406$). The relationships among H1, H2 and SE are not supported, as the relationships are not statistically significant (p values > 0.05). The key factors that influence students' enrollment decisions are PI, CO, FI and PC because these four factors have a significant positive effect on SE. In conclusion, this suggests that PI, CO, FI, and PC have meaningful and statistically significant impacts on SE, whereas UR and MD do not appear to have a strong or reliable influence on the outcome in this dataset.

Findings based on Research Question Two: What are the students' perceptions of the factors influencing their enrollment decisions at NUBB?

Table 5. Students' Perceptions of University Reputation

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
UR1	Nationally, the university is consistently ranked highly.	3.09	Agree
UR2	The academic staff at the university is well-respected and exceptionally qualified.	2.92	Agree
UR3	Employers have a positive impression of the university.	3.15	Agree
UR4	The university's reputation is enhanced by its alumni's success.	3.06	Agree
Total		3.05	Agree

According to the results of the survey, as shown by the statement Nationally, the university is consistently ranked highly (UR1), with a mean score of 3.09. This means that the participants agree with the statement. The second statement that the academic staff at the university is well respected and exceptionally qualified (UR2) receives a mean score of 2.92, which also shows that all participants agree. The statement that the university's reputation is enhanced by its alumni's success (UR4) scored a mean of 3.06, showing that alumni's success enhances student enrollment. These findings show that students view the university's academic staff, alumni success, and reputation favorably. Nonetheless, minor adjustments could be made to improve the perception of the credentials and credibility of academic personnel.

Table 6. Students' Perceptions of Multidisciplinary Aspects

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
MD1	The university is renowned for its outstanding academic programs in many fields.	3.01	Agree
MD2	The academic staff members are multidisciplinary experts.	2.87	Agree
MD3	In categories pertaining to each discipline, the university is well ranked.	3.05	Agree
MD4	The university has solid industry ties across a range of academic areas.	3.22	Agree
Total		3.03	Agree

Table 6 shows that students generally have a positive view of the university's academic reputation. The statement "The university is renowned for its outstanding academic programs" (MD1) received a mean score of 3.01, indicating that the university's programs are highly respected. The statement "The university is well ranked in various disciplines" (MD3) scored slightly higher at 3.05, suggesting that students recognize the university's strong academic standing. Additionally, "The university has solid industry ties across a range of academic areas" (MD4) received a mean score of 3.03, indicating that students' belief that these ties could enhance their academic and professional opportunities. While the academic staff's multidisciplinary expertise was viewed positively, it scored slightly lower. Overall, the findings indicate that students are generally satisfied with the university's academic programs and its reputation in both academic and professional circles.

Table 7. Students' Perceptions of the Influence of Peers

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
PI1	My decision about which university to go was affected by buddy.	2.18	Disagree
PI2	My opinions of the university are influenced by the attitudes and perspectives of my peers.	2.15	Disagree
PI3	My educational decisions are influenced by my friends' and family's educational backgrounds.	2.42	Disagree
PI4	My opinion of the university is influenced by social media and peer reviews.	2.62	Agree
PI5	I have chosen my academic programs based in part on the advice of my peers.	2.02	Disagree
Total		2.27	Disagree

Table 7 My decision about which university to visit was affected by buddy (PI1), with a mean score of 2.18, indicating that students do not believe that a friend has influenced their choice of university and suggesting that interpersonal interactions have little bearing on their choices. The statement that the university is influenced by social media and peer reviews (PI2) has a mean score of 2.15, suggesting that students do not believe that the views of their peers significantly influence their perceptions of the university. The statement that I have chosen my academic programs on the basis of the advice of my peers (PI5) received a mean score of 2.27, which shows that students typically choose their academic programs without consulting their peers, demonstrating a major contrast with the notion that program choices are based on peer recommendations. In general, students' choices of university and academic programs are not significantly impacted by their friends, family, or social networks. With the exception of peer reviews and social media, students appear to somewhat agree that these outside sources affect how they perceive the university.

Table 8. Students' Perceptions of Prospective Career Opportunity (CO)

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
CO1	Graduates from this university have good employment rates.	2.88	Agree
CO2	The career service centers at the institution are of outstanding caliber.	2.87	Agree
CO3	The university offers many of chances for internships and job placements.	2.99	Agree
CO4	Prospects for employment are enhanced by the size of the university's alumni network.	2.89	Agree
CO5	Employers hold the university in high regard.	3.16	Agree
Total		2.95	Agree

The results show that the statement Graduates from this university has good employment rates (CO1), with a mean of 2.88. Students agree that job statistics for graduates of this university are generally favorable. This implies that alumni's professional outcomes are expected to be favorable. The statement that the university offers many chances for internships and job placements (CO3) received a mean score of 2.99, indicating that students strongly agree that employers hold the university in high regard. This reflects a positive reputation in the job market, which can be crucial for future employment opportunities. In summary, institutions have a solid basis in terms of employer connections and career support, but there is even more room to improve services, especially in the areas of career counseling and alumni involvement.

Table 9. Students' Perceptions of the Influence of Their Families

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
FI1	My choices for schooling are influenced by my parents' expectations.	2.72	Agree
FI2	My choice to attend this university is influenced by my family's financial support.	2.74	Agree
FI3	My interests in academia have been shaped by my family.	2.86	Agree
FI4	My educational objectives are impacted by my family's educational history.	2.55	Agree
FI5	My choice of university is influenced by my family's location.	2.54	Agree
Total		2.68	Agree

Table 9 shows that the statement “My choices for schooling are influenced by my parents' expectations (FI1)” received a mean score of 2.71. This finding indicates that although the degree of agreement is not very high, students usually agree that their parents' expectations influence their school selections. The statement that my educational objectives are impacted by my family's educational history (FI4) received a mean score of 2.55. Although students believe that their family's educational background influences their educational objectives, the considerably lower score here suggests that this influence is viewed as moderate or less significant than other aspects. The statement “My choice of university is influenced by my family's location” received a mean score of 2.54. This finding demonstrates that family geography has a slight but discernible effect on college choice. Once more, it has slightly less of an impact than other elements, such as parental expectations or financial assistance. Overall, the students believe that their families have a significant effect on the decisions they make about their education, especially with respect to financial assistance and academic inclination. Family geography and educational background appear to have less of an impact. When examining how family dynamics affect students' support networks and decision-making, institutions or legislators might use these observations as a guide.

Table 10. Students' Perceptions of Personal Characteristics (PCs)

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
PC1	My educational goals coincide with the university's degree offerings.	2.98	Agree
PC2	My personality and the culture of the university seem to mesh well, in my opinion.	2.95	Agree
PC3	I'm interested in the extracurricular activities and social life that the institution offers.	2.98	Agree
PC4	The university encourages me to pursue my own objectives.	3.12	Agree
PC5	My decision to attend this university is influenced by my financial situation.	2.88	Agree
Total		2.97	Agree

Table 10 shows that the statement of my personality and the culture of the university seem to mesh well; in my opinion (PC2), the mean score was 2.95. This implies that most students believe that the university's offerings complement their learning objectives. Moreover, the statement “My decision to attend this university is influenced by my financial situation” (PC5) received a mean score of 2.88. This finding shows that while acknowledged as a factor, financial considerations are not the sole decider of their decision. While acknowledged as a factor, financial considerations are not the sole decider of their decision. The statement that the university encouraged me to

pursue my own objectives (PC4) received a mean score of 3.12. This shows that students believe that the university is very supportive of them, as they pursue their individual academic and professional goals. This is a very good outcome that shows a great sense of empowerment and encouragement. In conclusion, the ability of institutions to accommodate their academic and personal demands is often seen favorably by students. They believe that the university's programs and culture align well with their values and aspirations and that they are especially pleased with the support they receive in pursuing their own goals. Although not the primary determinant of their attendance, financial concerns definitely play a part.

Table 11. Students' Perceptions of Student Enrollment Decisions

Item	Statement	Mean	Description
SE1	My passion in the field is what motivated me to declare this as my major.	3.27	Strongly Agree
SE2	My major choice was influenced by the field's promising job opportunities.	3.06	Agree
SE3	My decision to major was influenced by instructors and counselors.	2.69	Agree
SE4	My major choice is in line with my personal talents and skills.	3.16	Agree
SE5	My choice of major was influenced by both family and friends.	2.51	Agree
Total		2.93	Agree

Table 11 shows that the statement that the decision to major was influenced by instructors and counselors (SE3) received a mean score of 2.69. This claim indicates that teachers and counselors have a moderate effect on students' choices. Although it has an impact, intrinsic reasons such as enthusiasm and career opportunities seem to be more significant. The statement My major choice is in line with my personal talents and skills (SE4) received a mean score of 3.16. The majority of the students believe that their major choice fits well with their individual skills and capabilities, which is encouraging because it shows that they are self-aware while making academic decisions. Closing follows the statement My passion in the field is what motivated me to declare this as my major (SE1) received a mean score of 3.27. Many students say that the main reason they chose their major was that they were passionate about the field. This implies that a major factor in their decision-making process is inner motivation. In summary, intrinsic motivation, such as a love for the subject and a fit with one's own skills, is what drives students most, followed by thoughts about future employment. Although they still have an impact, outside factors such as advisors and family members and friends are less significant. The general pattern points to a careful and self-driven major selection process that emphasizes future employment opportunities and individual interests.

In conclusion, students' perceptions of the factors influencing their enrollment decisions show that students view the university's academic staff, alumni success, and reputation favorably. Students are generally satisfied with the university's academic programs and reputation in both academic and professional circles. Institutions have a solid basis in terms of employer connections and career support. Students believe that their families have a significant effect on the decisions they make about their education, especially with respect to financial assistance and academic inclination. The ability of institutions to accommodate their academic and personal demands is often seen favorably by students, and intrinsic motivation, such as a love

for the subject and a fit with one's own skills, is what drives students most, followed by their thoughts about future employment. Moreover, students believe that the choices of university and academic programs are not significantly impacted by their friends, family, or social networks.

4.3 Findings based on research question 3: Determining whether there is a significant difference in students' enrollment decisions between male and female students on NUBB.

Table 12. Independent Sample t-Test between Sexes

Components	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	df	sig.
UR	Male	181	12.14	2.338	-.729	348	.466
	Female	169	12.31	1.816			
MD	Male	181	12.10	2.040	-.552	348	.581
	Female	169	12.22	1.804			
PI	Male	181	11.20	3.160	-1.216	348	.225
	Female	169	11.59	2.861			
CO	Male	181	14.95	2.723	1.224	348	.222
	Female	169	14.61	2.469			
FI	Male	181	13.10	2.688	-2.193	348	.029
	Female	169	13.75	2.824			
PC	Male	181	15.10	2.606	1.466	348	.144
	Female	169	14.70	2.427			
SE	Male	181	14.65	2.728	-.209	348	.834
	Female	169	14.71	2.453			

Table 12 compares the factors influencing the enrollment of male and female students in higher education. The analysis presents the mean values, standard deviations (SDs), and t test results to examine gender-based differences. For total UR (University Reputation), females had a slightly higher mean score (12.31) than males did (12.14), although the difference was not statistically significant ($t = -0.729$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.466$). Similarly, with respect to total MD (multidisciplinary aspects), females scored marginally higher (12.22) than males did (12.10), and this difference was also not significant ($t = -0.552$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.581$). In terms of total peer influence (PI), females scored higher (11.59) than males did (11.20), but this difference was not significant ($t = -1.216$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.225$). For total CO (prospective career opportunities), males had a higher score (14.95) than females did (14.61), and this difference was not significant ($t = 1.224$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.222$). For total FIs (family influences), males scored higher (181) than females did (169), and this difference was statistically significant ($t = -2.193$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.029$). For total PC (personal characteristics), males again scored higher (181) than females did (169), but this difference was not statistically significant ($t = 1.466$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.144$). Finally, in the total SE (Student Enrollment Decision), males had a slightly higher mean score (181) than females did (169), although this difference was also not statistically significant ($t = -0.209$, $df = 348$, $p = 0.834$). In conclusion, significant gender differences were found only in Family Influence (FI), where females had a higher mean income than males did, and the difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.029$). For all other variables (UR, MD, PI, CO, PC, and SE), there were no significant differences between males and females ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion

Regression analysis addressing the first research question identified parental influence (PI), prospective career opportunities (CO), family influence (FI), and personal characteristics (PCs) as the key factors significantly affecting students' enrollment decisions. These factors demonstrated substantial positive impacts on enrollment choices. In contrast, university reputation (UR) and multidisciplinary aspects (MDs) showed no significant influence, with a beta value of 0.050 and a p-value of 0.406. Por et al. (2014) similarly highlighted the significance of parental influence, high school teacher input, graduate quality, location, tuition fees, and institutional reputation in shaping students' university decisions, with statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, Sedahmed and Noureldien (2019) found that, in Sudan, institutional characteristics and admission processes were the primary determinants of student enrollment. Connie et al. (2022) emphasized the critical role of university reputation in shaping high school students' choices, mainly when linked to accreditation and recognition by national and international education authorities.

For the second research question, students expressed positive perceptions of the university's academic staff, alumni success, and overall reputation, indicating general satisfaction with the educational programs and the institution's standing in academic and professional contexts. A strong foundation in employer connections and career support further strengthened the university's appeal. Family influence, particularly financial assistance, and academic encouragement emerged as a crucial factor in educational decisions. Intrinsic motivation, such as passion for a subject and alignment with personal skills, was the primary driver of students' enrollment decisions, followed by career prospects. Interestingly, students perceived peers and social networks as having minimal influence on their academic and institutional choices. Rico-Briones (2019) similarly noted that personal decisions, bolstered by a university's reputation for high standards, competent faculty, and professional outcomes, were central to students' enrollment motivations.

Regarding the third research question, gender differences were statistically significant only for family influence (FI), where female students reported a more substantial impact than males ($p = 0.029$). For other variables, including UR, MD, PI, CO, PC, and SE, no significant gender differences were observed ($p > 0.05$). Supporting these findings, Spearman et al. (2016) observed that family influence had a more significant effect on female students, whereas peers and the social environment more influenced male students. Peer recommendations were notably more effective for males, while family support was pivotal in guiding female students' enrollment decisions. These findings underline the nuanced interplay of gender and social factors in shaping university enrollment choices.

Conclusion

This study identifies key factors influencing students' enrollment decisions at the National University of Battambang (NUBB). Parental influence, prospective career opportunities, family support, and personal characteristics were found to significantly positively impact enrollment decisions. Conversely, the university's reputation and multidisciplinary aspects showed no statistically significant effects. These findings suggest that while external perceptions of the university are valued, personal and familial factors are more pivotal in shaping enrollment choices. Students generally hold favorable views of the university's academic staff, alumni success, and overall

reputation. They are satisfied with the institution's educational offerings and its standing in both academic and professional domains. The university has established a strong foundation in career support and employer connections, further reinforcing its appeal. Family influence, particularly financial support, and academic encouragement emerged as a crucial determinant in educational decisions, highlighting the importance of family dynamics in the Cambodian context.

Intrinsic motivation—such as a passion for a chosen field and alignment with personal skills—remains the primary driver of enrollment decisions, followed by considerations about future employment. Interestingly, students perceive their peers and social networks as having minimal influence on their choices of university or academic programs. Gender-based analysis revealed a significant difference in family influence, with female students reporting a more substantial impact than males. No significant gender differences were observed for factors such as university reputation, multidisciplinary aspects, or career opportunities. These insights emphasize the need for higher education institutions to focus on fostering personalized support systems, enhancing career development programs, and engaging families in enrollment. By addressing these areas, universities can better align their strategies with students' motivations and needs, ultimately improving enrollment outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on research findings, researchers provide some recommendations:

To enhance enrollment outcomes, higher education institutions should address critical factors influencing student decisions, such as parental influence, career opportunities, family support, and personal characteristics. Universities can strengthen family engagement through workshops and informational sessions to emphasize the value of higher education. Career services should be expanded by creating robust internship programs, fostering employer partnerships, and showcasing alum success stories to highlight career readiness. Programs that align with students' personal goals and skills, such as leadership training and extracurricular activities, should be prioritized. Additionally, universities must enhance their branding by leveraging success stories, rankings, and unique attributes while improving their social media presence to engage prospective students.

Gender-specific needs should be addressed by offering tailored financial support and targeted programs for female students. Financial aid, scholarships, and flexible payment plans should be expanded to reduce financial barriers for all students. Peer and social influence channels can be strengthened through ambassador programs and digital platforms where prospective students connect with current students and alums. Finally, universities should continuously analyze data on enrollment factors to refine recruitment strategies, focusing on aligning academic offerings with market demands and fostering intrinsic motivations like passion for chosen fields and personal growth. By adopting these strategies, universities can better support student aspirations and create a more impactful enrollment experience.

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